

Characterisation of the Complexes Formed by the Interaction of Potassium Hexathiocyanato Chromium(III) with Amino Acids

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On the basis of magnetic, conductance, ir and electronic spectral studies, complexes of the type $K[Cr(NCS)_6A_n]$, $K[Cr(NCS)_6B]$, $K_n[Cr(NCS)_6X]$ and $K_n[Cr(NCS)_6Y]$ (A = leucine and isoleucine, B = iminodiacetic acid, X = histidine, glutamic acid, tyrosine, nicotinic acid, methionine or asparagine and Y = diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid) were found to have an octahedral structure. The ligand field strength of amino acids was in the order nicotinic acid < iminodiacetic acid < glutamic acid < tyrosine < histidine < isoleucine \approx leucine < diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid < methionine \approx asparagine.

A number of studies on the isolation of the interaction products of potassium hexathiocyanato chromium(III) and organic ligands, their chemical analysis, ir, conductance and magnetic measurements, have been reported¹⁻⁹. There was either a replacement of potassium ions¹⁰⁻¹³ or of thiocyanate ions^{14,15} with organic bases forming complexes of the type $Cr(SCN)_nL_{6-n}$ where L = aniline, acetamide, thiosemicarbazide, glycinate, alaninate, urea, thiourea, salicylate or ethylxanthate. More recently, studies with L = various amines have also been reported¹⁶. The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of some new complexes with L = amino acids. These complexes may be useful in mammalian metabolism¹⁷ and may also enhance the action of insulin.

Experimental

Materials and methods: All reagents used were of B.D.H., A.R. grade. The techniques, apparatus and methods of calculations were the same as reported earlier¹⁸. The reflectance spectra were recorded on a Carl Zeiss Spekol spectrophotometer fitted with a reflectance attachment of the type Rd/O.

Preparation of the complexes: Potassium hexathiocyanatochromium(III) tetrahydrate was prepared by literature method¹⁹. The complexes recorded in Table 1 were prepared by mixing the solutions of amino acids, one equivalent of KOH and $K_3[Cr(SCN)_6]$ in 1:1 ratio except complexes no. 9 and 10 where two moles of amino acids were used. The mixture was allowed to stand for 2 hr and then acetone was added. The grey, red or violet crystals produced were filtered, washed several times with 50% alcohol and dried at $\sim 70^\circ$. The complexes no. 2, 3, 6 and 7 are hygroscopic.

All the complexes are soluble in dimethylsulfoxide and complexes no. 2, 3, 6 and 7 are also soluble

in water. The results of analysis for metal, carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The molar conductances of complexes 2, 3, 6 and 7 in water and of the rest in dimethylsulfoxide were determined. The values ranging 220-260 and 95 and 390 mhos in the case of complexes 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8 and 9, 10 and 6, respectively indicated the presence of three, two and four ions. Table 2 contains the values of 10 Dq, B, $\beta_{3/8}$, ligand field stabilisation energies, molar conductances and experimental band energies with the transition energies calculated on the basis of various numerical procedures. The deviations from the experimental values $\delta\nu = \nu_{\text{calcd.}} - \nu_{\text{expt.}}$ are also given. The reflectance spectra of the solid complexes and the solution spectra in dimethylsulfoxide gave the bands at approximately the same wave numbers with a deviation of ± 20 indicating no structural changes on dissolution.

The third band (ν_3) has not been detected in the solution spectra. This is not unexpected as this band should be very weak, being forbidden both by the $g \rightarrow g$ selection rule and by other symmetry properties of the electronic wave functions of the terms. The charge transfer bands commence in the same region and ν_3 appears only as a shoulder on the large charge transfer band and hence is not clearly visible. The reported values of ν_3 in the first line of each complex (Table 2) have been taken from Tanabe Sugano diagram²⁰. The ratio of ν_2/ν_1 is 1.39 which fits with $10 Dq/B = 27.1$. It gives the value of $\nu_3/\nu_1 = 2.16$.

The spectral assignments are based on the energy level splitting originally proposed by Barnum²¹. 10 Dq was directly derived from first spin allowed band (ν_1). The energies of ν_2 and ν_3 have been calculated using standard equations¹⁸. The value

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Complex	Colour	Analysis % Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B. M.
			Cr	O	H	N	
1.	$K_2[Cr(NCS)_4(C_6H_8N_2O_2)]$	Red	10.00 (10.07)	23.15 (23.24)	1.56 (1.54)	18.85 (18.98)	3.68 3.65
2.	$K_2[Cr(NCS)_4(C_6H_{10}O_2NS)]$	Red	10.12 (10.21)	21.04 (21.22)	1.99 (1.96)	13.63 (13.75)	3.65
3.	$K_2[Cr(NCS)_4(C_4H_7N_2O_2)]$	Red	10.10 (10.19)	19.65 (18.82)	1.38 (1.37)	16.28 (16.47)	4.00
4.	$K_2[Cr(NCS)_4(C_2H_8NO_2)]$	Red	10.15 (10.23)	21.05 (21.25)	1.59 (1.57)	13.65 (13.77)	4.00
5.	$K_2[Cr(NCS)_4(C_6H_8NO_2)]$	Chocolate	10.08 (10.19)	30.29 (30.57)	1.58 (1.56)	13.65 (13.72)	3.65
6.	$K_2[Cr(NCS)_4(C_{14}H_{11}N_2O_{10})]$	Red	6.51 (6.56)	27.06 (27.27)	2.68 (2.65)	12.28 (12.37)	4.10
7.	$K_2[Cr(NCS)_4(C_4H_8NO_2)]$	Violet	11.82 (11.90)	19.18 (19.35)	1.14 (1.15)	12.81 (12.90)	4.20
8.	$K_2[Cr(NCS)_4(C_6H_8NO_2)]$	Grey	10.65 (10.76)	24.62 (24.84)	0.82 (0.83)	14.35 (14.49)	3.67
9.	$K[Cr(NCS)_4(C_6H_{11}NO_2)]$	Rose	11.10 (11.18)	35.85 (36.13)	5.20 (5.16)	11.92 (12.04)	3.67
10.	$K[Cr(NCS)_4(C_6H_{11}NO_2)]$	Chocolate	11.09 (11.18)	35.89 (36.19)	5.21 (5.16)	11.95 (12.04)	3.67

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND CALCULATED TRANSITION ENERGIES (cm^{-1})

Complex	Expt. of calculation	${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (ν_1)	${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2)	${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3)	B	β_{10}	$ \delta\nu $ cm^{-1}	$ \delta\nu $ (%)	LFSE kcal/ mole	Molar conductance (ohm^{-1})
1.	Exp.	17800	24700	38500	—	—	—	—	50.86	220
	(a)	10 Dq	Fitted	38946	683	0.744	+446	+1.145	52.86	260
	(b)	10 Dq	Fitted	24197	620	0.675	-603	-2.070		
(c)	10 Dq	Fitted	24464	38732	653	0.712	± 236	± 0.779		
2.	Exp.	18500	25600	39960	—	—	—	—	52.86	260
	(a)	10 Dq	Fitted	40413	701	0.763	+453	+1.120		
	(b)	10 Dq	Fitted	25079	636	0.693	-521	-2.070		
(c)	10 Dq	Fitted	25364	40200	671	0.731	± 240	± 0.755		
3.	Exp.	18500	25600	39960	—	—	—	—	52.86	260
	(a)	10 Dq	Fitted	40413	701	0.763	+453	+1.120		
	(b)	10 Dq	Fitted	25079	636	0.693	-521	-2.070		
(c)	10 Dq	Fitted	25364	40200	671	0.731	± 240	± 0.755		
4.	Exp.	17500	24300	37800	—	—	—	—	50	220
	(a)	10 Dq	Fitted	38308	674	0.734	+508	+1.320		
	(b)	10 Dq	Fitted	23718	601	0.655	-532	-2.450		
(c)	10 Dq	Fitted	24036	38064	640	0.697	± 254	± 0.895		
5.	Expt.	17700	24500	38250	—	—	—	—	50.57	230
	(a)	10 Dq	Fitted	38667	671	0.731	+417	+1.078		
	(b)	10 Dq	Fitted	24015	611	0.666	-485	-2.016		
(c)	10 Dq	Fitted	24276	38470	643	0.700	± 220	± 0.740		
6.	Exp.	18000	25000	38880	—	—	—	—	51.43	393
	(a)	10 Dq	Fitted	39400	693	0.755	+520	+1.810		
	(b)	10 Dq	Fitted	24403	619	0.674	-597	-2.446		
(c)	10 Dq	Fitted	24723	39158	659	0.717	± 277	± 0.553		
7.	Exp.	17000	23600	36720	—	—	—	—	48.75	250
	(a)	10 Dq	Fitted	37208	654	0.712	+508	+1.365		
	(b)	10 Dq	Fitted	22617	534	0.636	-983	-4.346		
(c)	10 Dq	Fitted	23343	36972	621	0.677	± 257	± 0.891		
8.	Exp.	16500	23500	35600	—	—	—	—	47.14	225
	(a)	10 Dq	Fitted	36427	717	0.770	+787	+2.160		
	(b)	10 Dq	Fitted	22316	561	0.620	-634	-3.070		
(c)	10 Dq	Fitted	22948	35152	640	0.690	± 552	± 1.960		
9.	Exp.	17950	24900	38770	—	—	—	—	51.29	95
	(a)	10 Dq	Fitted	39269	688	0.740	+498	+1.26		
	(b)	10 Dq	Fitted	24333	617	0.670	-567	-2.33		
(c)	10 Dq	Fitted	24642	39033	655	0.710	± 263	± 0.85		
10.	Exp.	17950	24900	38770	—	—	—	—	51.29	95
	(a)	10 Dq	Fitted	39269	688	0.740	+498	+1.26		
	(b)	10 Dq	Fitted	24333	617	0.670	-567	-2.33		
(c)	10 Dq	Fitted	24642	39033	655	0.710	± 263	± 0.85		

* Numbers are the same as in Table 1.

TABLE 3—STRETCHING FREQUENCIES (cm^{-1}) OF THE IMPORTANT BANDS OF COORDINATED AMINO ACIDS AND THIOCYANATE, DIFFERENCES FROM KSCN AND THE BOND TYPE**

Complex*	amino acids			thiocyanate				Bond type
	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{COO}-)$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$	$\Delta \nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$	$\Delta \nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$	
$\text{K}_2[\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6]$	—	—	—	2100 (vs)	n. a.	+51	—	M-S
1.	3450 (s, b)	1460 (m)	1640 (s)	2060 (vs)	800 (w)	+11	+51	M-N
		1110 (w)	1380 (s)					
2.	3450 (s, b)	1420 (m)	1620 (s)	2080 (vs)	790 (w)	+31	+41	M-N
		1200 (w)	1380 (s)					
3.	3450 (s, b)	1450 (m)	1620 (s)	2080 (vs)	790 (w)	+31	+41	M-N
		1200 (w)	1380 (s)					
4.	3450 (s, b)	1420 (m)	1680 (s)	2080 (vs)	800 (w)	+31	+51	M-N
		1160 (w)	1360 (w)					
5.	3400 (s, b)	1490 (m)	1650 (s)	2080 (vs)	780 (w)	+31	+31	M-N
		1140 (w)	1380 (m)					
6.	3450 (s, b)	1480 (m)	1640 (s)	2080 (vs)	800 (w)	+31	+51	M-N
		1140 (w)	1380 (w)					
7.	3400 (s, b)	1500 (m)	1640 (s)	2080 (vs)	820 (w)	+31	+71	M-N
		1280 (w)	1380 (w)					
8.	3400 (s, b)	1500 (m)	1620 (s)	2080 (vs)	810 (m)	+31	+61	M-N
		1220 (m)	1380 (m)					
9.	3450 (s, b)	1480 (m)	1640 (s)	2080 (vs)	800 (w)	+31	+51	M-N
		1140 (w)	1380 (m)					
10.	3450 (s, b)	1420 (w)	1640 (s)	2080 (vs)	790 (w)	+31	+41	M-N
		1100 (w)	1370 (s)					

vs = very strong, b = broad, m = medium, w = weak.

* Numbers are the same as in Table 1.

** The frequencies for KSCN are $\nu(\text{CN}) = 2049$ and $\nu(\text{CS}) = 749 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

$\nu\Delta = \nu(\text{complex}) - \nu(\text{KSCN})$.

of B calculated by three different methods have been substituted in the energy equations to evaluate the extra band energy of ν_2 and ν_3 transitions. The values given in Table 2 indicate that B and $\beta_{\beta, \beta}$ depend significantly on the method adopted for their calculation. The best fit for the transitions ν_2 and ν_3 is achieved by using the method (C) i.e. fitting the sum of second and third band, $[B = (\nu_2 + \nu_3 - 3\nu_1)/15]$, which is quite clear from the lowest values of deviation $|\delta\nu_{2,3}|$. Within the approximation of the three parameter ligand field theory, the energies of both the second and third bands (ν_2 and ν_3) are reproduced equally well. In addition, there does not exist a misfit of ν_3 which could be redistributed on ν_2 and ν_3 , if method (C) is applied. If this was true, a value of $|\delta\nu|$, intermediate between $|\delta\nu(a)|$ and $|\delta\nu(b)|$ would be expected. However, $|\delta\nu(c)|$ is always smaller than both $|\delta\nu(a)|$ and $|\delta\nu(b)|$.

The ligand field strength of different amino acids as indicated by the values of 10 Dq are in the order nicotinic acid < iminodiacetic acid < glutamic acid < tyrosine < histidine < isoleucine \approx leucine < diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid < methionine \approx asparagine. The effect of varying ligand field strength is also reflected in the magnetic moments of the complexes. Nicotinic acid, iminodiacetic acid, etc. in which the ligand field strength is very weak have values of 4.0-4.20 B.M., whereas methionine, asparagine, etc. have a moment of only around 3.65 B.M. The values of $\beta_{\beta, \beta}$ are also in support of the above observations.

IR studies : The important observations derived from the ir spectra of the amino acids and their

complexes are given in Table 3. The shift in frequencies of three fundamental modes of vibrations in the thiocyanate ion upon complexation has been widely used to determine the bond type. These frequencies in KSCN are 749 $\nu(\text{CS}$ stretching), 470 $\nu(\text{NCS}$ bending) and 2049 cm^{-1} $\nu(\text{CN}$ stretching). The C-S stretching frequency has often been considered as diagnostic of the metal bond since $\nu(\text{CS})$ is at 690-720 cm^{-1} for M-SCN and at 780-860 cm^{-1} for M-NCS complexes. The CN stretching frequencies of a thiocyanate complex increase in the order $\text{CNS} < \text{M-NCS} < \text{M-SCN} < \text{M-SCN-M}$. For M-SCN, it is above 2100 cm^{-1} and for M-NCS, it is below or equal to 2100 cm^{-1} ²². In general, $\nu(\text{CN})$ absorption is strong and exhibits a broad band for isothiocyanato and a sharp band for thiocyanato complexes.

According to Tramer²³, an increase in the frequency of $\nu(\text{CN})$ of 50-70 cm^{-1} relative to free thiocyanate ions is indicative of M-SCN coordination. For M-NCS, this decrease is less than 40 cm^{-1} . A large increase of 70-120 cm^{-1} is diagnostic of strong bridged complexes. For these cases, in which it is possible to assign $\nu(\text{CS})$, the differences from the free thiocyanate ion are an increase of 40-90 cm^{-1} for M-NCS and a decrease of 25-55 cm^{-1} for M-SCN.

In our case, when the thiocyanate is N-bonded, the $\nu(\text{CN})$ position is 2080 or 2060 cm^{-1} and $\nu(\text{CS})$ is around 800 cm^{-1} and when it is S-bonded, the $\nu(\text{CN})$ position is 2100 cm^{-1} . Some of the most important bands of amino acids given in Table 3 indicate their coordination with chromium through nitrogen of the amino group and the oxygen of the

carboxylic group. Both the antisymmetric and symmetric NH_2 stretching vibrations seem to have coupled and appear as strong broad bands at around 3400 cm^{-1} . The strong absorption bands observed in the region $1620\text{-}1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been assigned to the antisymmetric stretching modes of the ionised carboxylic group. The broadness of these bands suggests that probably the ionised carboxylic group has been coupled with the deformation NH_2 vibration in this region.

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